

Mental health of students during the COVID-19 epidemic in India- A study on students' perception

Shisira Bania¹, Bandita Biswal², Bijaya Kumar Pradhan³

¹Lecturer, Department of Education, Birmaharajpur College, Dist- Subarnapur, Odisha, India

²Lecturer, Department of History, Birmaharajpur College, Dist- Subarnapur, Odisha, India

³Lecturer, Department of Education, Birmaharajpur College, Dist- Subarnapur, Odisha, India

Corresponding Author- S. Bania, Email- shisirabania@gmail.com

Abstract

The present investigation aimed to assess the mental health of students during the COVID-19 epidemic in India. Data collected through a self-developed web-based online survey by using Google form. The non-probability snowball sampling technique was used for data collection. A total number of 448 students from different colleges belonging to age group 16-22 of Odisha, India were responded to the questionnaire between 10.05. 2020 to 30.05.2020 during the lockdown period in India. Different dimensions of mental health problem such as stress, worries, fear, anxiety, loneliness, anger, depression, irritability and concentration on the study were asked to rate on a four-point likert scale.

Irrespective of gender and age, the study revealed that the academic life of students has been affected because of COVID-19. Around 63 % of students agreed that they face difficulties in concentration often and every time, they study. 67.19 % of students agreed that they have worried about the future of their academic career. Although mental health problems of students such as loneliness, stress, anger, depression, irritability are not much serious, 60.44% out of total participants reported having panic and fear about the future.

Keywords :- Mental Health, Students, COVID-19 epidemic.

1. Introduction

Across the globe, pandemic influenza is widely considered to be one of the leading public health threats, currently facing the world today. (World Health Organisation [WHO], 2020). There have been numerous pandemics over the past century, most notable among them are “Bubonic Plague (1346-1353), HIV/AIDS Pandemic (2005-2012), The Spanish flu (a strain

of the H1N1 influenza virus;1918-1920), Russian flu (H2N2 or H3N8, 1889-1890), Hong kong flu (H3N2, 1968-1969), a second Russian flu pandemic (H1N1, 1977-1978), Swine flu (H1N1, 2009-2010) , Zika Virus Pandemic (2015-2016) (Blishe, 2005; Crosby, 2003; Doherty, 2013; Honigsbaum, 2014; Morens & Fauci,2017; WHO, 2010)” (Taylor, 2019) and at present Covid-19 (the Novel Corona virus).

Corona virus disease 2019 (COVID-19) caused by the novel Corona virus strain SARS-CoV-2 is a worldwide pandemic which has been declared a public health emergency of international concern by World Health Organisation (WHO). COVID-19, a cluster of acute respiratory illness with unknown causes, was first identified in Wuhan ,Hubei Province, of China during December 2019 and it was started to spread across the globe. (Zhao & Huang, 2020).The virus as on 05.06.2020 there were 6535354 confirmed positive cases 387155 deaths cases across the globe (WHO, Situation Report –137).

In India, the first case of the 2019–20 corona virus pandemic was reported on 30 January 2020, originating from China. On 22 March 2020, India observed a 14-hour voluntary public curfew at the instance of the Prime Minister Sri Narendra Modi. Further, on 24 March, the prime minister ordered a nationwide lockdown for 21 days. On 14 April, the prime minister extended the ongoing nationwide lockdown till 3 May and which is extending. As of 5th June 2020, the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare have confirmed a total of 226770 positive cases and 9851 deaths in the country.

2. Mental Health and COVID-19 Pandemic Epidemic- Literature Review

Research studies across the world revealed that “During any epidemics, the number of people whose mental health is affected tends to be greater than the number of people affected by the infection” (Reardon, 2015). Past tragedies have shown that the mental health implications can last longer and have greater prevalence than the epidemic itself and that the psychosocial and economic impacts can be incalculable if we consider their resonance in different contexts (Ornell et al., 2020). Zhao & Huang (2020) web-based study revealed a high prevalence of generalised anxiety disorder (GAD) and poor sleep quality in the Chinese population during COVID-19 outbreak. Shigemura et. al, (2020) reported that patients infected with COVID-19 (or suspected of being infected) may experience intense emotional and behavioural reactions, such as fear, boredom, loneliness, anxiety, insomnia or anger, etc. Wang

et al., (2020) conducted an online survey on Chinese people and found that approximately half of the interviewees classified the psychological impact of the epidemic as moderate to severe, and about a third reported moderate to severe anxiety. COVID19 is a biomedical disease and apart from the physical health implications the pandemic has instituted a cycle of negative thoughts and emotions in the people's mind. Roy & Sinha, 2020 reported that the COVID19 disease is not only has infected people in the body but the impact it has on people's minds is tremendous. Yuan et al. (2020) found that mental health problems of parents of hospitalized children during the epidemic were more serious, and the anxiety and depression were more obvious. The challenges and stress they experience could trigger common mental disorders, including anxiety and depressive disorders, and posttraumatic stress disorder, which in turn could result in hazards that exceed the consequences of the 2019-nCoV epidemic itself. Since the outbreak of COVID-19, the Chinese government has taken proactive measures to contain not only the spread of the novel corona virus but also that of psychological distress in the public (Bao et al., 2020).

3. Research Gap

The novel corona virus (COVID-19) pandemic is a situation that is affecting students physically as well as psychologically. The pandemic has caused strong feelings such as sadness, fear, anxiety, helplessness, uncertainty, loss of interest and hopelessness among students. However there found a dearth of systematic empirical research studies investigating the effect of college COVID-19 on mental health of students. Studies conducted so far are based upon studying general population, patients, and person infected with corona virus also many studies suffers from methodological shortcomings, and lack of ecological and population validity. The effect of college COVID-19 on mental health of students require to be examined empirically to resolve the discourse on dependence or independence of COVID-19 and mental health of students.

4. Objectives of the Study

- 4.1 To study the impact of Covid-19 on academic life of students.
- 4.2 To study the impact of Covid-19 on mental health of students.

5. Materials and methods

This cross sectional, observational study was carried out in the state of Odisha, India during the lockdown period declared by the Government of India. Data collected through a self-developed web-based online survey by using Google form. The non-probability snowball sampling technique was used for data collection. A total number of 448 students from different colleges belonging to age group 16-22 of Odisha, India were responded to the questionnaire between 10.05. 2020 to 30.05.2020 during the lockdown period in India.

From 448 respondents, 268 were female and 180 were male candidate. Further from the total respondents 20 students were studying in class XI and XII, 112 were studying in graduation 1st year, 105 were studying in graduation 2nd year, 142 were studying in graduation final year and 69 were studying in post graduation (table-1).

The questionnaire link was sent through social media such as e-mails, WhatsApp, Facebook. Upon receiving and clicking the link, the participants were automatically directed to the study information and informed consent. After they accepted the survey, they filled out the personal details like gender and their classes. Then a series of questions arose sequentially, which the participants had to answer. It was an online study. Participants with access to the Internet could take part in the study.

The online self-reported questionnaire developed by the investigators contained nine questions to be rated in the 4-point Likert scale format. Out of nine questions three questions were asked to know the impact of Covid-19 on students' academic life. Different dimensions of mental health problem such as stress, worries, fear, anxiety, loneliness, anger, depression, and irritability were asked to rate on a four-point likert scale ranging from never, rarely, often and every time.

Descriptive statistics have been used in the study to analyse the findings. Percentage and Bar diagrams have been used to estimate the results of the study.

Table : 1 Characterization of Participants

Age groups	Participants	Classes	Participants
16-17	20	XI & XII	20
18	112	Graduation 1 st year	112
19	105	Graduation 2 nd year	105
20	142	Graduation 3 rd year	142
21-22	69	Post Graduation	69
Gender	Participants		
Male	180		
Female	268		

6. Result

The global higher education market has undergone a drastic transformation as a result of the corona virus. The rate at which the Corona virus spread to various regions in India has caused central and state governments to shut down educational institutions and schools as a precautionary measure resulting in study interruption. Most universities have suspended teaching on campus and have switched to online instruction where possible. As a result, many board exams, university exams, college exams, the entrance were postponed which create not only uncertainty, worries among students but also impacted on their mental health.

6.1 Impact of Covid-19 on academic life of Students

The first issue of the survey was how the academic life of students was influenced by the COVID-19 pandemic. Figure 1 shows that 89.28 per cent of the respondent accepted that their study life was affected because of COVID-19. 48.66 per cent of students agreed that it was extremely affected; 22.32 per cent agreed that it was very affected; 18.30 per cent agreed that it was a little affected, and 10.71 per cent of students agreed that it was not affected at all.

Fig-1 Bar Graph on perception of students relating to impact of Covid-19 on their academic life

6.2 COVID-19 and concentration difficulties in study among students

The second question asked to know the concentration difficulties in their study. As per as figure 2, 40.18 per cent of students agreed that they face concentration difficulties every time, they study. 22.77 per cent often face concentration difficulties; 19.64 per cent rarely experience concentration difficulties, and 17.14 per cent of students have never had difficulty in concentrating on their studies.

Fig-2 Bar Graph on perception of students relating their concentration difficulties in their study due to COVID-19

6.3 COVID-19 and worries among students about the future of their academic careers

By posing the enquiry whether students are worried about the future of their academic careers, figures 3 shows that 49.78 per cent of students agreed that they are always worried about the future of their academic careers. 17.41 per cent were often worried; 19.87 per cent were rarely worried, and 12.95 per cent of students reported that they were never worried about the future of their academic careers.

Fig-3 Bar Graph on perception of students relating their worries about the future of their academic career due to COVID-19

6.4 Mental Health of students during COVID-19 pandemic

In the study, mental health problems of students of India were not much serious, expect 60.44% out of total participants were panic and fear about the future. 68.29 % of respondents reported that they never and rarely feel loneliness after lock down; 64.25 % respondent reported that they never and rarely feel stress after lock down declared by Govt. of India; 20.57 of respondent agreed that they feel angry often and always due to social and physical distance; and only 17.39 % students believed that due to loneliness, they irritated to family members.

Table 1 Mental Health of students during COVID-19 pandemic

Sl. No	Items	% of responses on various mental health problem (N = 448)	
		Never and rarely	Often and Every time
1.	Feeling loneliness due to lock down	68.29	31.71
2.	Feeling Stress due to lock down	64.25	35.75
3.	Feeling Angry due to social and physical distance	79.43	20.57
4.	Feeling Depressed due to “Study at home only”	60.28	39.72
5.	Panic and Fear about future	39.56	60.44
6.	Due to loneliness, Irritate to family members	82.61	17.39

7. Major Findings

1. 48.66 per cent of students agreed that their academic life is extremely affected; 22.32 per cent agreed that it was very affected; 18.30 per cent agreed that it was a little affected, and 10.71 per cent of students agreed that it was not affected at all.

2. 40.18 per cent of students agreed that they face concentration difficulties every time they study. 22.77 per cent often face concentration difficulties; 19.64 per cent rarely experience concentration difficulties, and 17.14 per cent of students have never had difficulty in concentrating on their studies.
3. 60.44% out of total participants were panic and fear about the future.
4. 68.29 % of respondents reported that they never and rarely feel loneliness after lock down;
5. 64.25 % respondent reported that they never and rarely feel stress after lock down declared by Govt. of India.
6. 20.57 of respondent agreed that they feel angry often and always due to social and physical distance.
7. Only 17.39 % students believed that due to loneliness, they irritated to family members.

8. Conclusion

Many studies conducted so far evaluated the mental health of hospitalized children, patients, corona infected people and general people. There is no study till date that evaluated the mental health perspectives of college students during the COVID-19 pandemic. The rate at which the Corona virus spread to various regions in India has caused central and state governments to shut down educational institutions and schools as a precautionary measure resulting in study interruption. As a result, many board exams, university exams, college exams, the entrance were postponed which create not only uncertainty, worries among students but also impacted on their mental health. The findings of the study revealed that academic life of students is affected; they are facing concentration difficulties while studying. However mental health problems of students such as loneliness, stress, anger, depression, irritability are not much serious.

Limitations

The study is limited to the college going students belonging to age group 16-22 years who had laptops, smartphones, with internet connectivity. The respondents belong to the college going students of the state Odisha only, so it should not be generalized to all students of India. The findings of these research studies may also differ from uneducated students of same age group.

References

- Banerjee, D. (2020). The COVID-19 outbreak: Crucial role the psychiatrists can play. *Asian Journal of Psychiatry*, 50, 102014. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajp.2020.102014>
- Bao, Y. Liu, J. J.,, Huang, X., Shi, J., & Lu, L. (2020). Mental health considerations for children quarantined because of COVID-19. *The Lancet Child & Adolescent Health*, 4(5), 347-349.
- Ornell, F., Schuch, J. B., Sordi, A. O., & Kessler, F. H. P. (2020). “Pandemic fear” and COVID-19: mental health burden and strategies. *Revista Brasileira de Psiquiatria (Sao Paulo, Brazil : 1999)*, 00(00), 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1516-4446-2020-0008>
- Reardon, S. (2015). Ebola's mental-health wounds linger in Africa: health-care workers struggle to help people who have been traumatized by the epidemic. *Nature*, 519(7541), 13+. Retrieved from https://link.gale.com/apps/doc/A404276279/AONE?u=oregon_sl&sid=AONE&xid=07af1c79
- Roy, D., & Sinha, K. (2020). Cognitive biases operating behind the rejection of government safety advisories during COVID19 Pandemic. *Asian Journal of Psychiatry*, 51, 102048. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajp.2020.102048>
- Shigemura, J., Ursano, R.J., Morganstein, J.C., Kurosawa, M., & Benedek, D.M. (2019) Public responses to the novel 2019 coronavirus (2019-nCoV) in Japan: mental health consequences and target populations. *Psychiatry Clin Neurosci*. 2020 Feb 8. doi: <http://10.1111/pcn.12988>.
- Taylor, S. (2019). *The Psychology of Pandemics: Preparing for the Next Global Outbreak of Infectious Disease*. Cambridge Scholar Publishing; UK.
- Wang C, Pan R, Wan X, Tan Y, Xu L, Ho CS, et al. Immediate psychological responses and associated factors during the initial stage of the 2019 coronavirus disease (covid-19) epidemic among the general population in China. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2020 Mar 6;17(5). pii: E1729. doi: <http://10.3390/ijerph17051729>.

World Health Organization. (2020). *Mental health and psychosocial considerations during the COVID- 19 outbreak, 18 March 2020* (No. WHO/2019-nCoV/MentalHealth/2020.1).
World Health Organization.

World Health Organization. (2020). *Mental health and psychosocial considerations during the COVID- 19 outbreak, 18 March 2020* (No. WHO/2019-nCoV/MentalHealth/2020.1).
World Health Organization.

Yuan, R., Xu, Q. hui, Xia, C. cui, Lou, C. yan, Xie, Z., Ge, Q. min, & Shao, Y. (2020).
Psychological status of parents of hospitalized children during the COVID-19 epidemic in
China. *Psychiatry Research*, 8(April).<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2020.112953>

Yao, H., Chen, J. H., & Xu, Y. F. (2020). Patients with mental health disorders in the COVID-19
epidemic. *The Lancet Psychiatry*, 7(4), e21.

Yang, Y., Li, W., Zhang, Q., Zhang, L., Cheung, T., & Xiang, Y. T. (2020). Mental health services
for older adults in China during the COVID-19 outbreak. *The Lancet Psychiatry*, 7(4),
e19.

Yuan, R., Xu, Q. H., Xia, C. C., Lou, C. Y., Xie, Z., Ge, Q. M., & Shao, Y. (2020). Psychological
status of parents of hospitalized children during the COVID-19 epidemic in China.
Psychiatry research, 112953.

Zhao, N., & Huang, Y. (2020). Chinese mental health burden during COVID-19 outbreak: a
web-based cross-sectional survey. *Asian Journal of Psychiatry*, 102052.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajp.2020.102052>

Zhu, Y., Chen, L., Ji, H., Xi, M., Fang, Y., Li, Y., 2020. The risk and prevention of novel
coronavirus pneumonia infections among inpatients in psychiatric hospitals.
Neurosci. Bull. 36 (3), 299–302.